

ORGANIZATION OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, a modern, reformed preschool education organization that meets the new requirements and the educator should have high knowledge and professional skills, the future educators are told that the real essence of preschool education is the cooperative activity of the child and the educator, starting from the student period. The tools and methods of organizing educational activities, the problems that arise in the educational process and their solutions are discussed.

Key words: preschool education organization, modern approach, innovation, pupil and educator, modern educational technologies, pedagogical technologies.

Аннотация: В данной статье современная, реформированная организация дошкольного образования, отвечающая новым требованиям и воспитатель должен обладать высокими знаниями и профессиональными навыками, будущим воспитателям сообщается, что настоящая сущность дошкольного образования заключается в совместной деятельности ребенка и воспитателя, начиная со студенческого периода. Рассматриваются средства и методы организации учебной деятельности, проблемы, возникающие в учебном процессе, и пути их решения.

Ключевые слова: организация дошкольного образования, современный подход, инновации, воспитанник и воспитатель, современные образовательные технологии, педагогические технологии.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yangi talablarga javob beruvchi zamonaviy, islohlashgan maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti hamda tarbiyachining yuksak bilim va kasbiy mahoratga ega bo'lishi, bo'lajak tarbiyachilarga talabalik davridan boshlab, maktabgacha ta'limning asl mohiyati bola va tarbiyachining hamkorlik faoliyati ekanligi, o'quv-tarbiya faoliyatini tashkil qilish vosita va usullarini o'quv-tarbiya jarayonida kelib chiqadigan muammolar va uning yechimini topishga doir fikr mulohazalar yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti, zamonaviy yondashuv, innovatsiya, tarbiyalanuvchi hamda tarbiyachi, zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari, pedagogic texnologiyalar.

Creation of conditions for all-round intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of pupils, improvement of the quality of preschool

education, radical improvement of quality preparation of pupils for school in preschool educational organizations, modern educational programs widely used in the world practice for the educational process and an order was adopted on the introduction of technologies, training of pedagogical personnel and provision of professional development.

The 21st century is the century of techniques and technologies. In this age, without innovation, without research, without creativity, a person cannot have his place in life as an independent individual.

The 21st century is the century of techniques and technologies. Today, in every family, technical devices - for example, mobile phones, television, computer, tablet, etc. are widely used in daily consumption. It is noteworthy that young children use these devices quickly and easily compared to adults. However, the level of goal orientation is very simple. In this sense, it is moving to the stage of providing preschool education organizations with complete technologies.

This expands the possibility of using visual aids in education based on modern technologies. In particular, it is advisable to use educational types of game programs for children in pre-school education institutions. In fact, today all the technical tools are the best weapon in our hands, the source of knowledge and the key to opportunities. This cooperation will serve a bright future only if we are not indifferent to the correct and conscious use of it from preschool education organizations, to create programs based on continuity and integrity aimed at raising our spirituality. Taking into account the interest of students in the preschool education system, it is even possible to divide them into groups and direct them to a certain field. The organization of a separate group also facilitates the goal of working with children who are interested in certain fields from an early age. If we consider that children's psyche, mood and interests are influenced even by the same clothes they wear, we can clearly feel that children's self-confidence and pride will be more stable. For example, the fact that all future patriotic children are dressed in military uniforms gives them great pleasure and responsibility.

The same reforms can be carried out in pre-school education organizations with other specializations. For example, clothes of a different color can be chosen for each group. In addition, various games are organized in order to inspire children's imagination to search for mines and mineral resources: it is important to encourage the child to hide some object in the upper part of the soil and find it with difficulty. It is even emphasized to the

little ones that they should search for it slowly and gently, otherwise they can cause harm. Such activities train students in the fresh air, exercise on the ground, and also form their ability to learn.

It is also useful to organize separate English and Russian language rooms for children in preschool educational institutions. Groups take turns training there. If children train using all innovative technology tools, toys, exhibitions, equipment will not be damaged and radiation will be prevented. It is important that walking through such separate rooms has a good effect on children. Their longing for such rooms will increase their interest in the lesson. The walls of the room are decorated in the same way so that the children feel as if they are in a foreign country when they enter the room. When the toys are given, the educator should teach the children the English name of each toy slowly.

English versions of cartoons also strengthen language learning. Therefore, it is important for the future educator to know information technologies and foreign languages well. Otherwise, effective results will be achieved if English language classes are conducted by special English teachers, not educators.

Reforms in the system of pre-school education are developing rapidly with the development of society and the country. Therefore, there will be a need for pre-school education organizations in the future near workshops and factories with huge permanent jobs. In this regard, organizing separate buses to bring children who live far away, thinking about the working procedures and programs of such institutions are also considered as special problems.

In short, by organizing innovative education in the preschool education system, we will achieve the following:

educating children intellectually and morally based on the rich national, cultural and historical heritage of our people and universal values;

- formation of national pride and patriotism in children;
- forming the need for education in children of preschool age, the desire to study, preparing them regularly for the educational process;
- development of children's thinking, formation of skills to express one's opinion intelligently and freely;
- ensuring physical and mental health of children.

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